

On Invertible Weighted Composition Operator on Hardy Space \mathbb{H}^2 .

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Abstract. In this paper we study the product of a weighted composition operator $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$ with the adjoint of a weighted composition operator $\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*$ on the Hardy space \mathbb{H}^2 . The order of the product give rise to different cases . We will try to completely describe when the operator $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*$ is invertible, isometric and unitary and when the operator $\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$ is isometric and unitary.

1. Introduction

Let U denote the open unite disc in the complex plan, let \mathbb{H}^∞ denote the collection of all holomorphic function on U and let \mathbb{H}^2 is consisting of all holomorphic self-map on U such that $f(z) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n z^n$ whose Maclaurin coefficients are square summable (i.e) $f(z) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} |a_n|^2 < \infty$. More precisely $f(z) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n z^n$ if and only if $\|f\| = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} |a_n|^2 < \infty$. The inner product inducing the \mathbb{H}^2 norm is given by $\langle f, g \rangle = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n \overline{b_n}$.

Given any holomorphic self-map φ on U , recall that the composition operator

is called the composition operator with symbol φ , is necessarily bounded. Let $f \in \mathbb{H}^\infty$, the operator $T_f: \mathbb{H}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{H}^2$ defined by

$$T_f(h(z)) = f(z)h(z), \quad \text{for all } z \in U, h \in \mathbb{H}^2$$

is called the Toeplitz operator with symbol f . Since $f \in \mathbb{H}^\infty$, then we call T_f a holomorphic Toeplitz operator. If T_f is a holomorphic Toeplitz operator, then the operator $T_f C_\varphi$ is bounded and has the form

$$T_f C_\varphi g = f(g \circ \varphi) \quad (g \in \mathbb{H}^2).$$

We call it the weighted composition operator with symbols f and φ [1] and [3], the linear operator

$$\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} g = f(g \circ \varphi) \quad (g \in \mathbb{H}^2).$$

We distinguish between the two symbols of weighted composition operator $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$, by calling f the multiplication symbol and φ composition symbol.

For given holomorphic self-maps f and φ of U , $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$ is bounded operator even if $f \notin \mathbb{H}^\infty$. To see a trivial example, consider $\varphi(z) = p$ where $p \in U$ and $f \in \mathbb{H}^2$, then for all $g \in \mathbb{H}^2$, we have

$$\| \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} g \|_2 = \|g(p)\| \|f\|_2 = \|f\|_2 |\langle g, K_p \rangle| \leq \|f\|_2 \|g\|_2 \|K_p\|_2.$$

In fact, if $f \in \mathbb{H}^\infty$, then $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$ is bounded operator on \mathbb{H}^2 with norm

$$\| \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \| = \|T_f C_\varphi\| \leq \|f\|_\infty \|C_\varphi\| = \|f\|_\infty \sqrt{\frac{1+|\varphi(0)|}{1-|\varphi(0)|}}.$$

2. Basic Concepts

We start this section, by giving the following results which are collect some properties of Toeplitz and composition operators.

Lemma (2.1):[4, 6] Let φ be a holomorphic self-map of U , then

- (a) $C_\varphi T_f = T_{f \circ \varphi} C_\varphi$.
- (b) $T_g T_f = T_{gf}$.
- (c) $T_{f+\gamma g} = T_f + \gamma T_g$.
- (d) $T_f^* = T_{\bar{f}}$.

Proposition (2.2):[1] Let φ and ψ be two holomorphic self-map of U , then

1. $C_\varphi^n = C_{\varphi_n}$ for all positive integer n .
2. C_φ is the identity operator if and only if φ is the identity map.
3. $C_\varphi = C_\psi$ if and only if $\varphi = \psi$.
4. The composition operator cannot be zero operator.

For each $\alpha \in U$, the reproducing kernel at α , defined by $K_\alpha(z) = \frac{1}{1-\bar{\alpha}z}$

It is easily seen for each $\alpha \in U$ and $f \in H^2$, $f(z) = \sum_{n=0}^\infty a_n z^n$ that

$$\langle f, K_\alpha \rangle = \sum_{n=0}^\infty a_n \alpha^n = f(\alpha).$$

When $\varphi(z) = (az + b)/cz + d$ is linear-fractional self-map of U , Cowen in [2] establishes $C_\varphi^* = T_g C_\sigma T_h^*$, where the Cowen auxiliary functions g , σ and h are defined as follows:

$$g(z) = \frac{1}{-bz+d}, \quad \sigma(z) = \frac{\bar{a}z-\bar{c}}{-bz+d} \quad \text{and} \quad h(z) = cz + d.$$

If φ is linear fractional self-map U , then $W_{f,\varphi}^* = (T_f C_\varphi)^* = C_\varphi^* T_f^* = T_g C_\sigma T_h^*$.

Proposition (2.4):[5] Let each of $\varphi_1, \varphi_2, \dots, \varphi_n$ be holomorphic self-maps of U and $f_1, f_2, \dots, f_n \in \mathbb{H}^\infty$, then

$$\mathcal{W}_{f_1, \varphi_1} \cdot \mathcal{W}_{f_2, \varphi_2} \dots \mathcal{W}_{f_n, \varphi_n} = T_h C_\phi$$

Where $T_h = f_1 \cdot (f_2 \circ \varphi_1) \cdot (f_3 \circ \varphi_2 \circ \varphi_1) \dots (f_n \circ \varphi_{n-1} \circ \varphi_{n-2} \circ \dots \circ \varphi_1)$ and

$$C_\phi = \phi_n \circ \phi_{n-1} \circ \dots \circ \phi_1.$$

Corollary (2.5): Let ϕ be a holomorphic self-map of U and $f \in \mathbb{H}^\infty$ then

$$\mathcal{W}_{f,\phi}^n = T_f (f \circ \phi) (f \circ \phi^2) \dots (f \circ \phi^{n-1}) C_{\phi^n}$$

The following lemma discuss the adjoint of weighted composition operator .

Lemma (2.6):[3] If the operator $\mathcal{W}_{f,\phi}: \mathbb{H}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{H}^2$ is bounded, then for each $\alpha \in U$

$$\mathcal{W}_{f,\phi}^* K_\alpha = \overline{f(\alpha)} K_{\phi(\alpha)}.$$

3- Invertible Weighted Composition Operator

In this section, we study the product of a weighted composition operator $\mathcal{W}_{f,\phi}$ with the adjoint of a weighted composition operator $\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*$ on the Hardy space \mathbb{H}^2 . The order of the product give rise to different cases. We will try to completely describe when the operator $\mathcal{W}_{f,\phi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*$ is invertible, isometric and unitary and when the operator $\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* \mathcal{W}_{f,\phi}$ is isometric and unitary. First we try to obtain some properties of the operator $\mathcal{W}_{f,\phi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*$.

Proposition (3.1): Suppose ϕ and ψ be two holomorphic self-map of U and $f \in \mathbb{H}^\infty$, such that 0 is not a fixed point of U then $\mathcal{W}_{f,\phi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*$ is self-adjoint if and only if

$$\psi(z) = \lambda \phi(z) \text{ , for all } z \in U.$$

Proof : Let $\beta \in U$, then for each $z \in U$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathcal{W}_{f,\phi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*)^* K_\beta(z) &= \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\phi}^* K_\beta(z) \\ &= T_f C_\psi \left(\overline{f(\beta)} K_{\phi(\beta)}(z) \right) \\ &= \overline{f(\beta)} f(z) K_{\phi(\beta)}(\psi(z)) \text{ .} \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand , for each $z \in U$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{W}_{f,\phi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* K_\beta(z) &= T_f C_\phi \left(\overline{f(\beta)} K_{\psi(\beta)}(z) \right) \\ &= \overline{f(\beta)} f(z) K_{\psi(\beta)}(\phi(z)) \text{ .} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\mathcal{W}_{f,\phi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*$ is self-adjoint if and only if for each $z \in U$

$$K_{\phi(\beta)}(\psi(z)) = K_{\psi(\beta)}(\phi(z))$$

Hence,

$$\frac{1}{1 - \overline{\phi(\beta)} \psi(z)} = \frac{1}{1 - \overline{\psi(\beta)} \phi(z)} \quad (1)$$

In particular letting $\beta = 0$ in equation (3.1), we get

$$\psi(z) = \lambda \phi(z) \text{ where } \lambda = \left(\frac{\psi(0)}{\phi(0)} \right) \text{ (note that } \phi(0) \neq 0 \text{) .} \quad \blacksquare$$

Recall that [2] an operator T is an isometry if $\|Tx\| = \|x\|$ for all x or equivalently $T^* T = I$.

Nordgren E.M [7] characterized the isometry composition operator as follows .

Theorem (3.2): A composition operator C_φ is an isometry if and only if φ is an inner function and $\varphi(0) = 0$.

Now , to characterize the inevitability of $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*$, we need the following results .

Lemma (3.3): Suppose that φ be a holomorphic self-map of U and $\in \mathbb{H}^\infty$. If $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$ is an isometry, then φ must be inner function and $\|f\| = 1$.

Proof : Let the operator $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$ is an isometry, then $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}^* \cdot \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} = I$. Thus for each $p \in U$, we have

$$\|\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} K_p\| = \|K_p\| , \text{ then } \|T_f C_\varphi K_p\| = \|K_p\| .$$

This implies that $\|f(K_p \circ \varphi)\| = \|K_p\|$. Hence, by taking $p = 0$, then $K_0 = 1$

and thus $\|f(1 \circ \varphi)\| = \|1\|$, then $\|f\| = 1$

In addition that, if $g(z) = z$, then it is clear that $\|g\| = 1$. Therefore

$$\|\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} g\| = \|g\| , \text{ and then } \|T_f C_\varphi g\| = \|g\| .$$

Thus , $\|f(g \circ \varphi)\| = \|g\|$, then $\|f \cdot \varphi\| = 1$.

Since $|\varphi(e^{it})| \leq 1$ a. e. $t \in [0, 2\pi)$

and both $\|f\|$ and $\|f \cdot \varphi\|$ are 1 . Then, by the integral representation of $\|f\|_{\mathbb{H}^2}$

$$\|f\|_{\mathbb{H}^2}^2 = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} |f(e^{it})|^2 dt .$$

So that $|\varphi(e^{it})| = 1$ a. e. on U , then φ is an inner function . ■

Gunatillake G. [5] studied the invertible weighted composition operator on Hardy space \mathbb{H}^2 . He give the following result .

Theorem (3.4):[5] The operator $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$ on \mathbb{H}^2 is invertible if and only if f is both bounded and bounded away from zero on the unit disc and φ is an automorphism of the unit disc. The inverse operator is the weighted composition operator $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}^{-1} = \mathcal{W}_{\frac{1}{(f \circ \varphi^{-1})}, \varphi^{-1}}$.

We are ready to discuss the inevitability of the operator of the operator $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*$.

Theorem (3.5): Suppose that φ and ψ be two holomorphic self-map of U and $f \in \mathbb{H}^\infty$. Then $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*$ is invertible if and only if each of $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$ and $\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}$ is invertible operator.

Proof : Suppose that $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*$ is invertible, then the operator $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*$ is one-to-one and onto. Hence, $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$ is onto. Therefore it is clear that, φ is non- constant map.

Thus, $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$ is one-to-one . Hence $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$ is invertible.

Now, since each of $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*$ and $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$ is invertible, then we have $\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}$ must be invertible operator.

The reverse induction follows immediately. ■

A straightforward consequence can be obtained from theorem (3.4).

Corollary (3.6): Suppose that φ and ψ be two holomorphic self-map of U and $f \in \mathbb{H}^\infty$. Then $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*$ is invertible if and only if f is bounded and bounded away from zero on U and each of φ and ψ is an automorphism of U .

Corollary (3.7): Let φ and ψ be two holomorphic self-map of U and $f \in \mathbb{H}^\infty$. If $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*$ is invertible, then $(\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*)^{-1} = C_{\psi^{-1}}^* \mathcal{W}_{[1/(f \circ \psi^{-1})](f \circ \varphi^{-1}), \varphi^{-1}}$.

Proof: Since by theorem (3.1.3) we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}^{-1} &= \mathcal{W}_{\frac{1}{(f \circ \varphi^{-1})}, \varphi^{-1}} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^{-1} = \mathcal{W}_{\frac{1}{(f \circ \psi^{-1})}, \psi^{-1}}. \text{ Then,} \\ (\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*)^{-1} &= (\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^{-1})^* = (\mathcal{W}_{\frac{1}{(f \circ \psi^{-1})}, \psi^{-1}})^* = (T_{\frac{1}{(f \circ \psi^{-1})}} C_{\psi^{-1}})^* \\ &= C_{\psi^{-1}}^* T_{\frac{1}{(f \circ \psi^{-1})}}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Hence, } (\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*)^{-1} &= (\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*)^{-1} (\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi})^{-1} \\ &= (C_{\psi^{-1}}^* T_{\frac{1}{(f \circ \psi^{-1})}}) \cdot (T_{\frac{1}{(f \circ \varphi^{-1})}} C_{\varphi^{-1}}) \\ &= C_{\psi^{-1}}^* T_{\frac{1}{(f \circ \psi^{-1})(f \circ \varphi^{-1})}} C_{\varphi^{-1}} \\ &= C_{\psi^{-1}}^* \mathcal{W}_{\frac{1}{(f \circ \psi^{-1})(f \circ \varphi^{-1})}, \varphi^{-1}}. \quad \blacksquare \end{aligned}$$

In the following, we give the necessary and sufficient condition to the operator $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*$ to be isometry first we need the next lemma.

Lemma (3.8)[9]: If T is isometry operator and S is unitary operator, then TS^* is an isometry.

Theorem (3.9): Suppose that φ and ψ be two holomorphic self-maps of U and $f \in \mathbb{H}^\infty$ such that $\|f\|_{\mathbb{H}^\infty} = 1$. Then $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*$ is an isometry if and only if $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$ is an isometry and $\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}$ is a unitary operator.

Proof: Suppose that $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*$ is an isometry, therefore

$$(\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*)^* \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* = I. \text{ Thus}$$

$$\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}^* \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* = I. \text{ Hence one can easily see that } \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi} \text{ is onto.}$$

This it is clear that, ψ is non-constant map. Therefore by lemma (2.4.3) we have $\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}$ is one-to-one.

Thus $\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}$ invertible. Therefore by theorem (3.1.5) and corollary (3.1.6) ψ must be an automorphism of U . So that there exists $\eta \in \partial U$ and $p \in U$, that for each $z \in U$

$$\psi(z) = \eta \left(\frac{p-z}{1-\bar{p}z} \right), \text{ where } \psi(p) = 0 .$$

But $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*$ is an isometry, then for every $p \in U$, we conclude that

$$\|\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* K_p\| = \|K_p\| .$$

Thus ,
$$\|\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} (\overline{f(p)} K_{\psi(p)})\| = \|K_p\| .$$

Hence ,
$$\|T_f C_\varphi (\overline{f(p)} K_0)\| = \|K_p\| .$$

Then ,
$$\|\overline{f(p)} T_f C_\varphi (K_0)\| = \|K_p\| .$$

Therefore ,
$$\|\overline{f(p)} f(K_0 \circ \varphi)\| = \|K_p\| .$$

But $(K_0 \circ \varphi = 1 \circ \varphi = 1)$,
$$\|\overline{f(p)} f\| = \|K_p\| .$$

Hence ,
$$|\overline{f(p)}| \|f\| = \|K_p\| .$$

Then ,
$$|\langle f, K_p \rangle| = \|K_p\| = \|f\| \|K_p\| .$$

Thus, by Cauchy –Schwartz inequality , we have

$$f(z) = \alpha K_p(z) = \frac{\alpha}{1-\bar{p}z} \quad \text{for some } \alpha \in \mathbb{C}$$

But $\|f\| = 1$, then it easily see that $f(z) = r \frac{K_p}{\|K_p\|}$ where $|r| = 1$ and $\psi(p) = 0$

Hence by theorem (2.9) we have $\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}$ is unitary operator .

Conversely , if $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$ is an isometry and $\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}$ is unitary , then

$$\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}^* \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} = \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi} = \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* = I \quad (2)$$

Hence from (3.2) we have

$$(\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*)^* \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* = \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}^* \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* = I .$$

Therefore $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*$ is an isometry ,as desired . ■

Corollary (3.10): Suppose φ and ψ be two holomorphic self-map of U and $f \in \mathbb{H}^\infty$ such that $\|f\|_{\mathbb{H}^\infty} = 1$. Then $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*$ is unitary if and only if each of $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$ and $\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}$ is an unitary operator .

Proof : Suppose that $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*$ is an unitary operator , then it is isometry. Therefore by theorem (3.9) we have $\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}$ is unitary operator . But since $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*$ is unitary, then $\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}^*$ is also unitary , thus by theorem (3.9) we have $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$ is unitary operator .

The converse is clear .

Now , the corollary (3.9) and theorem (2.9) we get the following consequence .

Corollary (3.11): Suppose φ and ψ be two holomorphic self-map of U and $f \in \mathbb{H}^\infty$ such that $\|f\|_{\mathbb{H}^\infty} = 1$. Then $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*$ is unitary if and only if each of φ and ψ is an automorphism of U and $f(z) = r \frac{K_p}{\|K_p\|}$ such that $p \in U$ where $|r| = 1$ and

$$\varphi(p) = \psi(p) = 0 .$$

We are in a position to examine when $\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$ dose admit characterization analogous to the operator $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*$, we first record result regarding norm .

Theorem (3.12): Suppose φ and ψ be two holomorphic self-map of U and $f \in \mathbb{H}^\infty$ such that $\|f\|_{\mathbb{H}^\infty} = |f(0)|^2 = 1$. Then $\|\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}\| = 1$ if and only if

$$\psi(0) = \varphi(0) = 0 .$$

Proof : If $\|\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}\| = 1$, then for each $\alpha, z \in U$ we get that

$$\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} K_\alpha(z) = \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* (f(z) K_\alpha(\varphi(z))) .$$

Thus by letting $\alpha = 0$ and $z = 0$, yields

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} K_\alpha(z) &= \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} K_0(0) \\ &= \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* (f(0) K_0 \circ \varphi(0)) \\ &= f(0) \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* (K_0) \\ &= f(0) \overline{f(0)} K_{\psi(0)} \\ &= |f(0)|^2 K_{\psi(0)} \\ &= K_{\psi(0)} . \end{aligned}$$

Hence , we have

$$\|K_{\psi(0)}\| \leq \|\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}\| = 1 \tag{3.3}$$

Thus ,

$$\|K_{\psi(0)}\|^2 = \frac{1}{1 - |\psi(0)|^2} \leq 1$$

which implies that $\psi(0) = 0$. But we know that ,

$$\|\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}\| = \|\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}\| = 1 .$$

Therefore , similarly we obtain that $\varphi(0) = 0$, as desired .

Conversely , assume that $\varphi(0) = \psi(0) = 0$. Thus ,

$$\begin{aligned} \|\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}\| &\leq \|\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}\| \|\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}\| \\ &\leq \|f\|_{\mathbb{H}^\infty}^2 \|C_\psi\| \|C_\varphi\| \end{aligned}$$

$$\leq \|f\|_{\mathbb{H}^\infty}^2 \sqrt{\frac{1 + |\varphi(0)| |1 + \psi(0)|}{1 - |\varphi(0)| |1 - \psi(0)|}}$$

And the hypothesis $\varphi(0) = \psi(0) = 0$ and $\|f\| = 1$ implies that

$\|\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}\| \leq 1$. Moreover, from (3) we have

$$\|\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}\| \geq \|K_{\psi(0)}\| = 1.$$

Hence, $\|\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}\| = 1$. ■

Corollary (3.13): Suppose φ and ψ be two holomorphic self-map of U and $f \in \mathbb{H}^\infty$ such that $\|f\|_{\mathbb{H}^\infty} = |f(0)|^2 = 1$. If $\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$ is an isometry, then $\psi(0) = \varphi(0) = 0$.

Proof : If $\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$ is an isometry, then its norm is one. Thus by theorem(3.1.12) we conclude that $\psi(0) = \varphi(0) = 0$. ■

Now, consider the case $\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$ is an isometry. We will require some preliminary results.

Proposition (3.14)[9]: Let S and T be contractive operators on a Hilbert space. If S^*T is an isometry, then T is an isometry and we have $T = SS^*T$.

Lemma (3.15)[9]: Suppose φ and ψ are holomorphic self-maps of U such that φ is non-constant and $C_\varphi = C_\psi T$ for some $T \in B(\mathbb{H}^2)$. Thus there is a holomorphic self-map α of U such that $T = C_\alpha$ and $\varphi = \alpha \circ \psi$.

Corollary (3.16):

Suppose φ and ψ are holomorphic self-maps of U such that $f \in \mathbb{H}^\infty \setminus \{0\}$. If φ is non-constant map and $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} = \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi} S$ for some $S \in B(\mathbb{H}^2)$. Then there is a holomorphic self-map α of U such that $S = C_\alpha$ and $\varphi = \alpha \circ \psi$.

Proof : It follows from $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} = \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi} S$ that for each $z \in U, g \in \mathbb{H}^2$

$f(z)C_\varphi g(z) = f(z)C_\psi S g(z)$. Hence, $C_\varphi = C_\psi S$. Hence the consequence follows immediately by lemma(3.15). ■

We are now in a position to analyze $\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$ in the case where the product is isometry.

Theorem (3.17): Suppose φ and ψ be two holomorphic self-map of U and $f \in \mathbb{H}^\infty$ such that $\|f\|_{\mathbb{H}^\infty} = |f(0)|^2 = 1$. If $\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$ is an isometry, each of φ and ψ is an inner function with $\psi(0) = \varphi(0) = 0$ and $\varphi = \alpha \circ \psi$ where $\alpha: U \rightarrow U$ is inner with $\alpha(0) = 0$.

Proof : Suppose $\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$ is an isometry. By corollary (3.1.13) we have $\psi(0) = \varphi(0) = 0$. This implies that,

$$\|\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}\| \leq \|f\|_{\mathbb{H}^\infty} \|C_\varphi\| \leq \|f\|_{\mathbb{H}^\infty} \sqrt{\frac{1 + |\varphi(0)|}{1 - |\varphi(0)|}} = 1.$$

Similarly $\|\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}\| \leq 1$, therefore each of $\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}$ and $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$ is contractive on \mathbb{H}^2 . Now, applying corollary (3.1.16) with $S = \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}$ and $T = \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$, we get that $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$ is isometry and $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} =$

$\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi} \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$. Therefore, by lemma (3.3) we get that φ is an inner function. Thus it is clear that φ is non-constant.

Now, by corollary (3.16) there exists a holomorphic self-map α of U such that

$$C_\alpha = \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} \quad \text{and} \quad \varphi = \alpha \circ \psi.$$

Now, C_α is an isometry, then by theorem (3.2) we have α is inner function such that $\alpha(0) = 0$. Since each of φ and α is inner function, then ψ is also.

Conversely, if each of φ and ψ is inner function such that $\varphi(0) = \psi(0) = 0$

$\varphi = \alpha \circ \psi$ where $\alpha: U \rightarrow U$ is inner with $\alpha(0) = 0$. Using the identity $C_\alpha = \mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$, we obtain by theorem (3.2) that C_α is an isometry, as desired. ■

Now, we are ready to use the isometric characterization to describe precisely when $\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$ is a unitary operator.

Corollary (3.18): Suppose φ and ψ be two holomorphic self-map of U and $f \in \mathbb{H}^\infty$ such that $\|f\|_{\mathbb{H}^\infty} = |f(0)|^2 = 1$. Then $\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$ is unitary if and only if each of φ and ψ is an inner function with $\psi(0) = \varphi(0) = 0$ and there exists inner function α with $\alpha(0) = 0$ such that $\varphi = \alpha \circ \psi$.

Proof: Suppose $\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$ is unitary, then by theorem (3.17) both φ and ψ is an inner function with $\psi(0) = \varphi(0) = 0$ and there exists inner function α with $\alpha(0) = 0$ such that $\varphi = \alpha \circ \psi$.

As in theorem (3.17) we have $\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi} = C_\alpha$, and so C_α is unitary. This implies $\alpha(z) = \lambda z$ for some λ with $|\lambda| = 1$. Therefore $\varphi(z) = \lambda\psi(z)$. The reverse induction is clear. ■

Now, we are ready to recover the inevitability of the operator $\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$. We need the following lemma.

Lemma (3.19)[10]: Suppose φ be univalent, holomorphic self-map of U . Then C_φ has closed range on \mathbb{H}^2 if and only if φ is an automorphism of U .

Theorem (3.20): Suppose φ and ψ be two holomorphic self-map of U such that ψ is univalent and $f \in \mathbb{H}^2$ which is bounded and bounded away from zero. Then $\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$ is invertible if and only if each of φ and ψ are automorphism of U .

Proof: Suppose that $\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* \mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$ is invertible, then $\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^* = C_\psi^* T_f^*$ is onto. Therefore, it is clear that C_ψ^* is onto. This implies that C_ψ is bounded from below and so the range of C_ψ is closed. Thus by lemma (3.19) we have ψ is an automorphism. Therefore by applying theorem (3.4) we have that $\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}$ is invertible operator. Hence $\mathcal{W}_{f,\psi}^*$ is invertible and then $\mathcal{W}_{f,\varphi}$ is invertible.

Therefore again by theorem (3.4) that φ is an automorphism.

The converse is follows immediately by theorem (3.4). ■

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